

Understanding the Scope of Artificial Intelligence and Change in Leadership Goals – A Theoretical Perspective

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Abstract

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is basically the new normal. AI can perform functions that are usually performed by humans such as human-interaction, learning and problem-solving. AI is one of the oldest fields in computer science and it came into picture in around 1950s. This was the time when machines were seen playing chess, answering puzzles and solving algebraic equations.

As machines becomes increasingly capable, the scope of AI in business applications is growing rapidly. Since AI is developed only for purpose of improve, and ultimately replace human intelligence, it is tempting to take AI as a threat to human leadership. As of now, the competitive advantage for humans is that till now there is no such machine which can 100% replace humans. But down the line, in another 10 years, there is no such reason to believe that leadership will be spared by the impact of AI.

Managers should sense big changes as AI becomes integrated into their workflows. The study will analyze the emergence of AI and the changes that AI will bring to core management tasks. The paper gives insights about how managers, in the coming future, will serve as bridges between AI systems and their team members.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Leadership, Management, Humans, Business, Technology.

Introduction

“AI today is pretty cool; AI today is something which can help you out in almost anything. But apparently AI is rising to such an extent that it is mastering almost all the stuffs that humans perform and hence it is making us to witness the scenario in which it will be replacing humans.” (Milo Jones - TEDX IE. MADRID)

Milo Jones mentioned the various transformations that AI is bringing to the make the life of the humans easy, frictionless, smooth and smart. AI is making the life better and consistent by bringing improvements and efficiency. He mentioned the pros and cons of AI and discussed the effects of AI on leadership roles. There are various downsides of AI, but basically it depends

on how the AI technology is been used and managed responsibly for efficient development and advances.

“Artificial Intelligence” is the area of computer science which deals with creation of such machines that work and react like humans. It aims to create intelligent machines which serves objectives like planning, problem solving, and reasoning by learning and building its knowledge over the period.

Artificial intelligence can reduce the work pressure on the employees by smoothening the process and handling various routine jobs in a smart and efficient way. It can give a competitive edge over the competitors.

Artificial intelligence is gradually simulating the intelligence that only humans were having at one point of time. It is not only simulating the intelligence, it is developing its own knowledge by initiating common sense, perception, reasoning, and problem-solving abilities.

Research Objectives

Following are the objectives of the study:

1. To find out the emergence of artificial intelligence in core management tasks.
2. To evaluate how AI can revolutionize leadership process.

Research Methodology

The following study uses descriptive research design to analyse the emergence of artificial intelligence and the changes it is going to bring to core management tasks. Secondary data collection method is used for the study. The data has been collected through the articles published over the various online websites, blogs, podcasts, newspapers published by various research organizations and online sources.

Emergence of AI in Core Management Tasks

Technology has become an important part of all the organizations. One can not even think of the business without technology in it. AI has surely revolutionized the way companies were working earlier, and how they are working now. With the extreme advances in the field on AI, it has developed leadership skills like humans. AI now can develop strategies by planning and even can solve problems that are related to humans.

In current scenario, artificial intelligence together with robotics are coming and taking our jobs. Because of the advances in the AI, it is predicted to drive the biggest technology disruption in the workplace since the Industrial Revolution. Its impact is such that in coming future, AI is predicted to take almost 33-50% of the routine tasks performed at present. The prior waves of new technology mainly impacted the workers rather than managers, but now AI has radically started to take on the knowledge work including the core management tasks.

Though artificial intelligence is impacting the traditional work pattern followed in the organizations, but the organizations can achieve their goals in less time as AI offers organizations with great opportunities. Artificial intelligence is helping the managers in automating the complex functions such as data collection and gathering information. It helps the managers in using the data to its fullest and bringing out the important observations out of the data.

Managers spend most of their time in doing the administrative work which is basically the information-based work with some repeated patterns. These administrative jobs can be done very easily by the artificial intelligence because AI can handle data much efficiently when compared to humans. Also, it will reduce the term ‘human error’ from the context as there will be no human activity interfering the process. So, what about the leaders? What will they do? They can save on

time because of AI and hence can utilize the saved time to spend on interesting companies, projects and new ideas. They can utilize the time do all those works which machines cannot perform. Eventually it will help the businesses to increase their volume and quality.

How Artificial Intelligence can revolutionize the leadership process?

The new artificial intelligence technology knows how to comprehend (understanding the connection and correlation between different patterns), sense (observing and registration of data), act (to assess the impact of various alternatives) and learn (learning from own experiences; more data, better algorithm). This makes the new AI to stand out different from traditional AI concept. This new technology helps the organization in handling the core management tasks.

The very fundamental of leadership is to look out for the welfare of the subordinates and to lead by examples. With the help of artificial intelligence, one can achieve the efficiency among the process of leadership by focusing on the strategies and goal of the organization.

Though the idea of artificial intelligence looks fancy because of the automation that it provides, but still the leadership goals cannot be achieved without the involvement of humans in it. It seems to be a paradox, but as artificial intelligence technology will grow, people will need to grow their skills as well. When AI system starts coming into picture, it would be more of synchronizing the complex machine processes which requires more collaboration with different machines and bodies, which can be done by humans only.

Future managers need to be bilingual as they need to know language of the both the sides. They will need to have a proper leadership skill along with the good knowledge of technology. They should know the uses of various technologies, and the knowledge of how to use it. It cannot be only computers who can run the business, it must be a team of humans and computers.

A good strategy can be a combination of a weak human, machine and a good process. But it can never be a combination of a strong human, machine and an inferior process. Artificial intelligence system is not about replicating the humans, it's about finding the best combinations of what humans are good at and what machines are good at. Machines and humans together can take great decisions.

Benefits of AI in Leadership Process

1.1 Faster Decisions: Using artificial intelligence with the cognitive technologies can help the organisations in making faster decisions and carry out the actions quicker.

1.2 Automation of routine works: One of the massive advantages of artificial intelligence is its potential to complete routine tasks through introducing the automation that will increase productivity.

1.3 Dealing with mundane tasks: AI through intrincating automation can even remove boring tasks from the leaders and free them up to be increasingly creative in the management tasks.

1.4 Avoiding errors: The phrase “human errors” was born because human, naturally, makes mistakes from time to time. Computers however, do not make such mistakes – that is, of course, assuming they are programmed properly.

1.5 Taking risks on behalf of humans: With artificial intelligence, you can surely lessen the risks you expose humans to in the name of research. Using AI in this manner can lead to benefits such as demand forecasting, medical diagnosis and oil exploration.

Conclusion

“The future of AI is supporting and augmenting human capabilities such that a human-AI team is stronger than either alone.” - Missy Cummings (Director, Humans & Autonomy Lab, Duke University)

Machines and humans together can take great decisions. Both can complement each other but we always tend to think that artificial intelligence leads to automation, and hence it will lead to unemployment. Yes, it seems true, but it is the one of the several scenarios. It will not be the same case always. On one hand AI is leading to unemployment, and on other hand it is creating opportunities for those who are open to accept the changes and are ready to develop skills related to the artificial intelligence science. The managers need to know about their roles and responsibilities and must be confident about that. Although artificial intelligence may reduce the dependency on the manpower but still employers will be requiring efficient manager, skilled workers, and professional to tackle with the system.

The technology has changed the way of working system. The credit goes to artificial intelligence that the world has become smaller and future generation will use advance technologies for the better leadership and better management.

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